

GDI Milestone 41 - Report: Initial Definition of the process to validate distributed and federated learning infrastructure on GDI

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Distributed vs. federated; analysis vs. learning

Distributed Analysis refers to the process of analyzing data that is distributed across multiple locations or nodes, without necessarily involving collaborative learning or model training. The main goal of distributed analysis is to leverage the computational resources available at each location to perform data analysis tasks.

Distributed Learning refers to the process of training a machine learning model using data that is distributed across multiple locations or nodes. The main goal of distributed learning is to overcome the limitations of centralized learning by allowing each node to locally train a portion of the model using its own data and then combine the local models to obtain a global model.

Federated Analysis refers to the process of analyzing data that is distributed across multiple locations or nodes in a privacy-preserving manner. The main goal of federated analysis is to enable collaborative analysis of sensitive data without compromising data privacy or security.

Federated Learning refers to the process of training a machine learning model using data that is distributed across multiple locations or nodes in a privacy-preserving manner. The main goal of federated learning is to enable collaborative learning of sensitive data without compromising data privacy or security.

The main difference between **distributed analysis/learning** and **federated analysis/learning** is the privacy-preserving aspect of the latter. While **distributed analysis/learning** focuses on leveraging the computational resources available at multiple locations to perform analysis or model training, **federated analysis/learning** aims to achieve this while preserving the privacy and security of the data.

The architecture of federated learning

HORIZONTAL FEDERATED LEARNING

In this architecture, data sources have the same features, but different instances or samples of data. The goal is to train a model that can generalize well across these instances without sharing raw data.

VERTICAL FEDERATED LEARNING

In this architecture, data sources have different features, and the goal is to jointly train a model across these features without sharing raw data.

The organization within federated learning

CENTRALIZED ORGANIZATION

In a centralized organization, there is a single central entity, typically a server and aggregator, that coordinates and controls the entire federated learning process. Clients send their local model updates to the central entity, which aggregates the updates and updates the global model.

HIERARCHICAL ORGANIZATION

In a hierarchical organization, multiple levels of aggregation are used to combine model updates from different clients. Typically, clients at lower levels of the hierarchy aggregate their model updates locally and then send the aggregated updates to clients at higher levels for further aggregation. This hierarchical approach can reduce communication overhead and improve scalability, as aggregation happens at different levels of the hierarchy.

REGIONAL ORGANIZATION

In a regional organization, clients are organized into regional groups based on a specific criteria (that can be geographic or technical for instance). Each regional group has its own aggregator. The regional aggregators then exchange updates with a central aggregator, which further aggregates the updates and updates the global model. This architecture is useful when there are regional data distribution patterns or regulatory requirements that need to be considered.

DECENTRALIZED ORGANIZATION

In a decentralized organization, there is no central aggregator. Instead, clients directly communicate and collaborate with each other to train the global model. Clients share their model updates with each other and combine them locally to update their own models.

The downside of federated learning

COMMUNICATION OVERHEAD

Federated learning relies on communication between the central server (aka. aggregator) and the distributed clients for exchanging model updates. This communication can introduce overhead in terms of bandwidth, latency, and energy consumption, especially when dealing with large-scale datasets or slow or unreliable network connections. Efficient management of communication is crucial in federated learning to minimize these overheads.

COMPUTATIONAL OVERHEAD

Federated learning may require clients to perform local model training, which can impose computational overhead on resource-constrained devices or environments with limited computing capabilities.

PRIVACY AND SECURITY RISKS

Federated learning requires sharing of model updates among clients, which may contain sensitive information about the local data. Ensuring privacy and security of the data during model updates and aggregation is a critical concern in federated learning. Techniques such as encryption, differential privacy, and secure multi-party computation are used to mitigate privacy and security risks, but they may introduce additional computational overhead or implementation complexities.

LACK OF CENTRALIZED CONTROL

Federated learning is designed to distribute the model training process across multiple clients, which can lead to challenges in centralized control and coordination. Ensuring convergence and consistency of the global model across all clients, handling failures or dropouts of clients, and managing the overall training process can be complex in a decentralized setting.

DATA HETEROGENEITY

In federated learning, the data used for training the local models at different clients can be heterogeneous in terms of distribution, quality, and quantity. This can pose challenges in achieving a globally optimal model, as the models need to be combined from diverse data sources with varying characteristics. Addressing data heterogeneity and developing effective methods for aggregating and reconciling diverse models is an ongoing research area in federated learning.

MODEL FAIRNESS AND BIAS

Federated learning can potentially exacerbate model fairness and bias issues, as local models at different clients may have different data distributions and biases. Ensuring fairness and mitigating bias in the global model requires careful consideration of data representation, model aggregation, and bias detection techniques.

How does federated learning (typically) work

Assuming we are on a horizontal architecture and a centralized organization, the way of how federated learning would work is following six steps.

The following figure shows the first four steps that cover the global initialization, a local training and the update of the initial global model.

But, as stated before, the full process involve 6 steps that are:

1. Initialize a initial global model
2. Distribute the initial global model
3. Train initial global model on local data
4. Collect local models and aggregate them into a trained global model
5. Evaluate trained global model
6. Repeat until 2-5 until appropriate metric is reached

EVALUATION OF MODELS AND THEIR AGGREGATION

In federated learning, the evaluation of the global model is performed by aggregating the model updates obtained from multiple clients, and then applying these updates to the global model.

The evaluation process can vary depending on the specific federated learning architecture and organization being used. In a horizontal federated learning setting and centralized organization as shown before, the evaluation can be performed by computing the average (or weighted average) of the model updates received from the clients. The central aggregator can use various aggregation techniques apart from simple averaging. Some more complex strategies are federated averaging and "FedAvg+", which incorporates adaptive learning rates to combine the model updates received from the clients.

Then, the resulting global model is then tested on a held-out validation set to measure its performance. The evaluation metrics used for this performance-test can vary depending on the specific task and application. Common evaluation metrics include accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and area under the curve (AUC) for classification tasks, and mean squared error (MSE), root mean squared error (RMSE), and mean absolute error (MAE) for regression tasks.

The degradation of models

Model degradation is a phenomenon that occurs in federated learning when the performance of the global model begins to decrease over time, despite the fact that more data is being used to train the model.

POSSIBLE DEGRADATION FACTORS

There are several factors that can contribute to model degradation in federated learning.

Non-independent and identically distributed data (non-i.i.d)

When the data distribution among the clients is not identical and independently distributed, the local models at different clients may converge to different optima, leading to conflicting updates and a decrease in global model performance.

Inadequate training data

Inadequate or insufficient training data can lead to overfitting of the model, where the model performs well on the training data but poorly on the testing data.

Poor model architecture

Choosing an inappropriate model architecture, such as one that is too complex or too simple for the given task, can lead to poor model performance and degradation over time.

Hyperparameter selection

Poor choices of hyperparameters, such as learning rate, batch size, and number of epochs, can lead to overfitting or underfitting of the model, which can reduce its overall performance.

DEGRADATION-AVOIDANCE STRATEGIES

There are several techniques available to avoid model degradation in federated learning. These techniques aim to improve the convergence of the local models and reduce the impact of non-i.i.d. data, ultimately leading to better global model performance.

Adaptive learning rates

Adaptive learning rates involve adjusting the learning rate of the model dynamically based on the gradient magnitudes of the local updates. This can help prevent the model from overfitting or underfitting and improve its generalization ability.

Early stopping

Early stopping involves stopping the training process when the model's performance on the validation set starts to degrade. This can help prevent overfitting and improve the model's generalization ability.

Model pruning

Model pruning involves removing unimportant weights or connections from the model to reduce its size and complexity. This can help improve the model's speed and generalization ability.

Model compression

Model compression involves reducing the size of the model by using techniques such as quantization, pruning, and low-rank factorization.

Client selection

Client selection strategies involve selecting a subset of clients to participate in the federated learning process based on data quality and task relevance. This can help improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the federated learning process and prevent the model from being degraded by low-quality updates or outliers.

These techniques can be used in both centralized and federated learning settings to prevent model degradation and improve the performance of machine learning models over time.

Federated Learning at GDI

GDI'S MODEL REPOSITORY

A repository of machine learning models is useful for sharing and reusing models across different applications and domains. Two areas are key on a model repository:

- Providing raw models allows users to customize and fine-tune the models to their specific tasks in a specific domains
- Providing trained models is useful for tasks that have similar data and conditions and are in the same of similar domain, avoiding the need to (re-)train the model

A good example of a repository of machine learning models is Hugging Face, which offers pre-trained models, APIs, and tools for fine-tuning and creating new models in the field of natural language processing. But they are not alone:

1. TensorFlow Hub: A repository of pre-trained models and modules for TensorFlow.
2. PyTorch Hub: A collection of pre-trained models and tools for PyTorch.
3. Model Zoo: A repository of pre-trained models and code examples for a wide range of machine learning tasks.
4. OpenAI API: A platform for accessing state-of-the-art language models and other AI models through an API.
5. Papers with Code: A platform for sharing and discovering machine learning papers and code, including pre-trained models.

GDI'S MODEL REQUIREMENTS

Model validation

From the technical point of view, we can use synthetic data for evaluating a federated learning model. To do so, the evaluation process is similar process to evaluate a traditional machine learning model:

- Split the synthetic data into training and testing sets.
- Train the federated learning model.
- Evaluate the model performance using the desired metric.
- Repeat the evaluation with different synthetic data.

It is important to note that the performance of the federated learning model on synthetic data may not always generalize well to real-world data, especially if the synthetic data is significantly different from the real data. Therefore, it is essential to consider the quality and representativeness of the synthetic data when evaluating the federated learning model.

But, despite all, this is the general process of technically evaluating a model before allowing it to be included into GDI's repository.

MODEL'S DATA PRIVACY PRESERVATION

Evaluating the privacy and security implications of the evaluation of a federated learning model is a really complex task that requires expertise in both machine learning and data privacy:

- **Data Privacy.** Evaluating the privacy implications of the model can involve analyzing the types of data that are being used in the design, train, evaluation, and storage of the model.
- **Model Security.** Evaluating the security of the model involves multiple factors that might depend on the task but some of them are the model robustness, model poisoning attacks, and the security of the communication channel between the clients and the central server.
- **Ethical considerations.** In addition to any legal compliance, it is important to consider ethical implications of the evaluation of the model. It is important to ensure that the evaluation (both technical and in terms of data privacy) is conducted in a fair and transparent manner. Moreover, this can also be extended to the data used to train the model as well as the data being evaluated, that must be ethically collected.

To evaluate the privacy and security implications of the evaluation of a model, it is important to follow best practices in data handling, model evaluation, and regulatory compliance.

CONCLUSION

At the moment, the technology for federated learning is not yet fully developed, and we are unable to make specific recommendations. We are conducting a thorough review of the current state of federated learning and have found that there are only a few frameworks available, each with their own unique solutions and use cases. One of our short term goals is to analyze the technological requirements of various use cases and map them to the capabilities of each framework.

